

Burnout in Infection Control Practitioners During Public Health Crisis Events: A Mixed Methods Systematic Review *Protocol*

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Aims

- ❑ Evaluate the quantitative, qualitative, and primary mixed-method studies pertaining to burnout among infection control practitioners
- ❑ Public health crisis events (major outbreaks, epidemics, pandemics),
- ❑ High-income countries from 2002 to present.

Source: Stock image

karōshi

The 3 symptoms of burnout (Maslach Burnout Inventory)

Source: www.themusingmind.com

Methodology

- ❑ Mixed-methods systematic review (MMSR)
- ❑ Convergent integrated approach (JBI methodology)
- ❑ Quantitative data will be transformed into qualitized data following data extraction.
- ❑ Resulting in textual descriptions or narrative interpretations facilitating integration with data already extracted from the qualitative studies, to respond directly to the review question.

[Source: JBI Model of EBHC | JBI](#)

Conclusion

- Give voice to infection control practitioners & nurses globally.
- Investigate overall measurement, antecedents, factors, outcomes as well as the meaning and impact of burnout in this cohort.
- **Richer understanding of burnout and associated factors.**
- **Inform healthcare professionals, senior leadership & policy makers and researchers.**

Source: Stock image

QUESTIONS

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